

The Influence of Work-Life Quality and Work Environment on Work-life balance Mediated By Job Satisfaction and Work Commitment at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh

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Abstract: This study aims to examine the work-life quality and work environment role in work-life balance mediated by job satisfaction and work commitment at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh. The population is 350 ASN at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh. The number of samples was determined using the basis of the Structural Model test method, which is based on the formula 7 times the indicator, where the indicators total 25 so that a total sample of 175 people is obtained. Data were collected thru questionnaires. The results prove that the variables Work-life quality, Environment, Satisfaction, Work Commitment, and Work-life balance at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh are good; Work-life quality and Environment affect Satisfaction; Work-life quality and Environment affect Work Commitment; Work-life Quality, Environment, Satisfaction, and Work Commitment affect Work-life balance; and Satisfaction and Commitment partially mediate the Work-life quality and Environment contribution to Work-life balance. These findings explain that the work-life balance at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh is a function of improving the work-life quality, environmental adjustment, increasing satisfaction, and strengthening work commitment.

Keywords: Work-life quality, work environment, job satisfaction, work commitment, Work-life balance.

I. Introduction

Organizations are very dependent on human resources in it and also organizations need a balance between the employee's role inside of work and outside of work. This will show a balance between employee activities at work and personal life, family, friends, and when the individual is in society. This study will be carried out at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh, Indonesia. The Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh task works for managing the water resources in the river basins in Aceh Province.

Employee work-life balance can be assessed from the level of discipline of employees at work. An undisciplined employee is an employee who is unable to manage his work interests outside of work, thus creating a separate conflict. An interview with the Head of the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh reveals that overall the work discipline of employees is not optimal. The results of observations in the field show that some employees do not comply with the regulations set by the agency, such as coming late to work, morning apples that are not followed and some employees do not report when they do not come to work and are still seen at the shop to drink and have breakfast at the specified working hours, or during the afternoon break which exceeds the time, in terms of dress, it looks untidy and does not wear footwear following the provisions of the agency. If this continues, it can be detrimental to the agency.

Many factors affect work-life balance, namely employee satisfaction at work, commitment, work-life quality, and work environment. (Parkes & Langford, 2015) also said that work-life balance contributes to employee engagement (satisfaction and commitment). Work-life quality is also seen as capable of increasing the participation and contribution of members or employees to the organization. An unhealthy environment will also have an impact on individual satisfaction in achieving a balance between life and work. High levels of work-family conflict occur when the demands of work-life create problems meeting the demands of family life due to a poor work environment. A lot of research has been done to examine the contingency theory, but more has been done from a business and organizational perspective and very little from public organizations like this research. Based on the phenomenon that occurs, it is not following the

supposed causality theory. This study model was a combination of previous models and based on facts that occur in the field.

II. Literature

Work-life balance

(McDonald & Bradley, 2005) states that work-life balance is the level of satisfaction associated with multiple roles in one's life. Work-life balance is generally associated with balancing or maintaining all aspects of human life. (Fisher, Bulger, & Smith, 2009) defines work-life balance as an effort made by individuals to balance two or more roles that are undertaken. When a person experiences a work-life balance in his life, it can be ascertained that the individual is very satisfied with the situation he is living in. An employee will not consider himself successful if his personal and family needs are not properly met.

Job satisfaction

To be able to improve good work performance, the organization must be able to fulfill and also increase the satisfaction of its employees at work. According to (Simanjuntak, 2020) Job satisfaction is a set of positive work behaviors that are rooted in strong awareness, and strong beliefs, and accompanied by a strong commitment to an integrated work paradigm. Someone who feels satisfied at work will make every effort to complete the work assignments given to him with all the abilities he has so that his performance will increase. Organizations need employees who can work better, faster, and more thoroughly, to get this, job satisfaction must be maintained and maintained and also paid attention to (DeCenzo, Robbins, & Verhulst, 2018) ; (Kanwar, Singh, & Kodwani, 2009). In this study, the variable "job satisfaction" will often be called "satisfaction"

Work Commitment

(Supriyono, 2019) and (Coryanata, 2014), defines work commitment as encouragement from within the individual to do something to support the success of the organization following its goals and prioritize the interests of the organization over its interests. Commitment will make the organization more productive (Luthans, 2012). Strong work commitment within the individual will cause the individual to try hard to achieve organizational goals following the goals and interests of the organization (Coryanata, 2014) and will have a positive outlook and try to do their best for the benefit of the organization. The participation role in the budgeting process on performance will be high if the work commitment of the leadership is high (Coryanata, 2014). In this study, the variable "work commitment" will often be called "commitment".

Work-life quality

According to (Mangkuprawira, 2011), Work-life quality is the level of satisfaction, motivation, involvement, and experience of commitment of individuals regarding their life at work. (Cascio, 2018) states Work-life quality is one of the important objectives in meeting the needs and desires of employees. (Cascio, 2018) said that work-life quality can be defined as employees' perceptions of their mental and physical well-being while working. There are two views regarding the meaning of Work-life quality. First, work-life quality is some circumstances and practices of the organization. Second, work-life quality is the employee's perception that they want to feel safe, feel satisfied, and get the opportunity to grow and develop as human beings (Hapsari, 2013).

Work environment

The work environment is a very important part of when employees carry out work activities. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to work optimally. According to (Sunyoto, 2015) The work environment is everything that exists around the workers and which can influence them in carrying out the assigned tasks. According to (Sedarmayanti, 2016) The work environment is the overall tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as a group. In this study, the variable "work environment" will often be called "environment".

Model and Hypothesis

The study model and hypothesis are formulated as follows.

Figure 1. Influence Between Variables

Hypothesis

- H1: Work-life quality, environment, satisfaction, commitment, and work-life balance at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh are good.
- H2: Work-life quality affects satisfaction
- H3: Environment affects Satisfaction
- H4: Work-life quality affects Commitment
- H5: Environment affects Commitment
- H6: Work-life quality influences Work-life balance
- H7: Environment affects work-life balance
- H8: Satisfaction affects work-life balance
- H9: Commitment influences work-life balance
- H10: Work-life quality influences Work-life balance through Satisfaction
- H11: Environment influences work-life balance through the satisfaction
- H12: Work-life quality influences Work-life balance through Commitment
- H13: Environment influences Work-life balance through Commitment

III. Method

The research location was at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh. The object was all apparatus(employees) at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh. Meanwhile, the object of research is Work-life quality, environment, satisfaction, commitment, and work-life balance at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh. The population was 350 civil servants at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh. The sample was determined based on Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) as the method of analysis, namely using the formula 7 times the indicators totaling 25 indicators to obtain a sample of 175 people. Data were collected thru questionnaires. This study used a multichotomous questionnaire (many answer choices) using a Likert scale. The measurement indicators were:

1. To measure work-life balance, the indicators used were as disclosed by(McDonald, Brown, & Bradley, 2005)namely a) time balance, b) involvement balance and c) satisfaction balance
2. To measure satisfaction, the indicators used were as disclosed by(DeCenzo et al., 2018)namely a) salary, b) job, c) partner, d) boss, and e) promotion.
3. To measure commitment, the indicators used were as disclosed by(Wibowo, 2017)namely: a) a sense of belonging e, b) a sense of attachment, c) the meaning of the organization personally, d) will not leave, e) pride, and f) loyalty.
4. To measure Work-life quality, the indicators used were as disclosed by(Afsar, 2014)namely a) participating decision-making, b) nature of work, c) rewards and recognition, d) work environment, e) managerial relationship, and f) performance enhancement.
5. To measure the work environment, the indicators used were as disclosed by(Sedarmayanti, 2016)namely a) lighting, b) air circulation, c) noise, d) bad smell, e) security

IV. Result

H1: Descriptive Test

The respondents' perceptions obtained the results as described below.

Table 1. Perceptions

Variable	Average	Cut Off	Information
Work-life quality	3.94	3.41	Good
Environment	3.86		Good
Satisfaction	4.10		Good
Commitment	3.96		Good
Work-life balance	4.08		Good

Table 1 above explains that the average respondent's perception of all variables has obtained a value > 3.41. The acquisition of this value proves that the descriptive hypothesis testing is accepted.

Direct Effect

The model analysis is shown below.

Figure 2. Structural Test

The results obtained from direct hypothesis testing are presented below.

Table 2. Regressions

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Satisfaction	<---	Work-life quality	0.331	0.084	3.450	0.000
Commitment	<---	Work-life quality	0.296	0.071	3.118	0.002
Commitment	<---	Environment	0.536	0.106	4.803	0.000
Satisfaction	<---	Environment	0.757	0.106	6.207	0.000
Work-life Balance	<---	Work-life quality	0.449	0.081	4.115	0.000
Work-life Balance	<---	Environment	0.343	0.082	2.071	0.038
Work-lifeBalance	<---	Satisfaction	0.412	0.108	3.843	0.000
Work-lifeBalance	<---	Commitment	0.259	0.069	2.474	0.013

These results formulate the equation as follows:

Satisfaction = 0.331 Work-life quality + 0.757 Environment

Commitment = 0.296 Work-life quality + 0.536 Environment

Work-life balance = 0.449 Work-life quality + 0.343 Environment + 0.412 Satisfaction + 0.259 Commitment

Based on the results can be explained as follows:

H2: Work-life quality contribution to Satisfaction

Testing H2 resulted in a significance value (P) of 0.000. This describes work-life quality affects satisfaction. The work-life quality role size in satisfaction is 0.331 or 33.1%. This explains that if the work-life quality increases by 1 unit, it will increase satisfaction by 0.331 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. (Cascio, 2018) explains creating good work-life quality has the goal to create a work climate that can encourage employees to increase satisfaction. (Aruldoss, Kowalski, & Parayitam, 2021), (Arief, Purwana, & Saptono, 2021) also found that work-life quality negatively affected satisfaction.

H3: Environment contribution to Satisfaction

Testing H3 produces P 0.000. This explains the environment affects satisfaction. The Environment role size in Satisfaction is 0.757 or 75.7%. This explains that if the environment improves by 1 unit, satisfaction will increase by 0.757 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. A good environment will create ease of carrying out tasks. Fulfillment of a good environment will have an impact on employee satisfaction. (Yunanda, 2013) found that the work environment affected the satisfaction

H4: Work-life quality contribution to Commitment

Testing H4 resulted in P 0.002. This reveals that work-life quality affects commitment. The work-life quality contribution size to commitment is 0.296 or 29.6%. This explains that if the work-life quality increases by 1 unit, then the commitment will increase by 0.296 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. The psychological dynamics of work-life quality and commitment are when an employee's work-life quality is good, his commitment will be high (Hamidi, Jufri, & Karta, 2019). (Indaswari, 2014) found that work-life quality affected commitment.

H5: Environment contribution to Commitment

Testing H5 resulted in P 0.000. This means the Environment influences Commitment. The Environment role size in Commitment is 0.536 or 53.6%. This explains that if the environment improves by 1 unit, then the commitment will increase by 0.536 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. An employee needs to have a basic work character that is formed from his work environment so that it contributes to his commitment to work. High job involvement means taking sides with the job (Griffin, Phillips, & Gully, 2016).

H6: Work-life quality contribution to Work-life balance

Testing H6 resulted in P 0.000. This explains the work-life quality affects work-life balance. The work-life quality role size in work-life balance is 0.449 or 44.9%. This explains if the work-life quality increases by 1 unit, it will increase the work-life balance by 0.449 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. Work-life quality is the level of satisfaction, motivation, involvement, and commitment that plays a role in balancing life and work.

H7: Environment contribution to work-life balance

Testing H7 resulted in P 0.038. This reveals the environment affects work-life balance. The environment role size in work-life balance is 0.343 or 34.3%. This explains that if the environment improves by 1 unit, it will increase the work-life balance by 0.343 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. An unhealthy environment will have an impact on individual satisfaction in achieving a work-life balance. High work-family conflict levels occur when the demands of work-life create problems in meeting the demands of family life caused by a bad environment. (Rahmayati, 2021) found that the environment affected the work-life balance

H8: Satisfaction contribution to Work-life balance

Testing H8 produces P 0.000. This describes satisfaction affects work-life balance. The satisfaction role size in work-life balance is 0.412 or 41.2%. This explains that if satisfaction increases by 1 unit, it will balance work-life by 0.412 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change. According to (Sutrisno, 2019) Human

resources who cannot face the demands of globalization tend to see work as a burden.(Moedy, 2013)and(Aruldoss et al., 2021)found that satisfaction affected work-life balance.

H9: Commitment contribution to Work-life balance

Testing H9 resulted in P 0.013. This describes commitment affects work-life balance. The commitment role size inwork-life balance is 0.259 or 25.9%. This explains that if commitment increases by 1 unit, it will balance work-life by 0.259 units. The influence shown is a positive influence or a unidirectional change.(Parkes & Langford, 2015)also said that Work-life balance contributed to higher productivity and lower organizational turnover.

Indirect Effect

H10: Work-life quality contribution to Work-life balance through Satisfaction

Testing the satisfaction mediation on the work-life quality contribution to work-life balance shows the result as follows:

Figure 3. Work-life quality Contribution to work-life balance through satisfaction

The Sobel test obtained a result of 2.740 (<1.96). Thus, satisfaction acts as a mediator on work-life quality contribution to work-life balance. Because satisfaction affected and acted as a mediator, work-life quality affected work-life balance, so the satisfaction mediating nature on work-life quality contribution to work-life balance is as a partial mediator, where the results are as follows:

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a 0.331	Sobel test: 2.74082977	0.04975574	0.00612842
b 0.412	Aroian test: 2.69637637	0.05057603	0.00700984
s _a 0.084	Goodman test: 2.78755688	0.04892169	0.00531071
s _b 0.108	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 4. Testing Work-life quality Contribution to Work-life balance Through Satisfaction

H11: Environment contribution to Work-life balance through Satisfaction

Testing the Satisfaction mediation on the work-life quality contribution to work-life balance is illustrated as follows:

Figure 6. Environment on Work-life balance through Satisfaction

The Sobel test obtained a result of 3.364 (<1.96). This proves satisfaction acts as a mediator on the environment contribution to work-life balance. Because satisfaction affected and acted as a mediator, the environment affected work-life balance, so the satisfaction mediating nature on the work-life quality contribution to work-life balance is as a partial mediator. Below is the calculation display.

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.757	Sobel test:	3.3648366	0.00076589
b	0.412	Aroian test:	3.33946191	0.00083941
s _a	0.106	Goodman test:	3.39079864	0.00069689
s _b	0.108	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 7. Testing Environment Contribution to Work-life balance Through Satisfaction

H12: Work-life quality towards Work-life balance through Commitment

Testing the Commitment mediation on the Work-life quality contribution to Commitment as illustrated below:

Figure 8. Work-life quality Contribution to work-life balance through Commitment

The Sobel test obtained a result of 2.789 (<1.96). This reveals commitment acts as a mediator on work-life quality contribution to work-life balance. Because commitment affected and acted as a mediating variable, work-life quality affected work-life balance, so the commitment mediating nature on the work-life quality contribution to work-life balance is as a partial mediator. Below is the calculation display.

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.296	Sobel test:	2.78954353	0.00527824
b	0.259	Aroian test:	2.74625239	0.00602804
s _a	0.071	Goodman test:	2.8349487	0.0045833
s _b	0.069	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 9. Testing Work-life quality Contribution to Work-life balance Through Commitment

H13: Environment contribution to Work-life balance through Commitment

Testing the commitment mediation on the environmental influence model on commitment is illustrated as follows:

Figure 10. Environment Contribution to work-life balance through Commitment

The Sobel test obtained a result of 3.013 (<1.96). This explains commitment acts as a mediator between the environment and work-life balance. So, because commitment affected and acted as a mediator, Environment affected work-life balance, the commitment mediating nature on the Environment contribution to Work-life quality is as a partial mediator. Below is the calculation display.

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a 0.536	Sobel test: 3.01397127	0.04606016	0.00257852
b 0.259	Aroian test: 2.97667645	0.04663725	0.00291391
s _a 0.106	Goodman test: 3.05270396	0.04547575	0.0022679
s _b 0.069	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 11. Testing Environment Contribution to Work-life balance Through Commitment

V. Conclusion

The results concluded that at the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh, the Work-life quality, Environment, Satisfaction, Commitment, and Work-life balance were good; Work-life quality affects satisfaction; Environmental Quality affects Satisfaction; Work-life quality affects Commitment; Environment influences Commitment; Work-life quality affects Work-life balance; Environment influences Work-life balance; Satisfaction affects Work-life balance; Commitment influences Work-life balance; Commitment fully mediates the Work-life quality contribution to Work-life balance; Commitment to fully mediate Environmental influences on Work-life balance; Satisfaction mediates fully the Work-life quality contribution to Work-life balance; and Satisfaction fully mediates the Environment contribution to Work-life balance. These findings explain that work-life balance in the Sumatera River Regional Office I Aceh is a function of improving the work-life quality, environmental adjustment, increasing satisfaction, and strengthening work commitments. This academically proven model can also form the basis of future research. The limitations are on the variables and subjects studied. Practitioners, especially the subject of this study, can take advantage of this model to be considered in setting policies for their employees in the future.

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